

The views expressed in this material do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

IMPERIAL

Beyond the Tick-Box: Barriers and Solutions to Inclusive Infrastructure Planning

AUTHORS: Marissa Bergman ¹, Stephanie Hirmer ², Julia Tomei ³, Beatrice Stockport ⁴, Gerald Arhin ⁵

Summary

Energy and transport infrastructures are central to development trajectories in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), yet the ways in which they are planned, financed, and delivered often reproduce or deepen existing inequalities for historically marginalised and vulnerable groups. Gender Equality, Disability, and Social Inclusion (GEDSI – also known as GESI) frameworks seek to address these disparities, but in practice are frequently treated as an add-on rather than a core principle of infrastructure planning.

To interrogate why GEDSI integration in energy and transport decision-making remains limited, and to identify pragmatic entry points for change, Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) convened a one-day multi-stakeholder workshop at the University of Oxford in March 2025. Thirty participants from research, policy, finance, and development organisations across the UK, US, Denmark, and Kenya worked through a series of breakout sessions to identify and prioritise barriers to GEDSI integration and explore opportunities for coordinated, cross-sector action.

Key Messages

- Workshop participants identified 18 barriers to meaningful GEDSI integration in energy and transport infrastructure planning, grouped into five themes: policy and governance, financial and economic, research and expertise, institutional and organisational, and social and cultural.
- Across these themes, lack of accountability, a weak business case for GEDSI, limited data and expertise, unjust decision-making processes, and exclusionary cultural norms emerged as the most critical barriers.
- These barriers are systemic and mutually reinforcing, meaning that interventions focused on a singular entry point – such as policy reform, data collection, or training – are unlikely to be sufficient on their own.
- Participants highlighted three broad opportunities for collaborative action: building a stronger case study evidence

A rural woman trained as a “Solar Mama” technician by the Indian NGO Barefoot College.

base of successful GEDSI implementation, improving knowledge-sharing through accessible platforms, and aligning existing GEDSI frameworks and metrics to reduce duplication and increase collective impact.

Introduction

Energy and transport infrastructures underpin socio-economic development, shaping access to services, livelihoods, and resilience [1, 2]. For LMICs, where foundational infrastructure and energy demand is expanding, decisions about these systems are central to development trajectories and delivering sustainable, low-carbon transitions [3, 4]. However, the ways in which the benefits and burdens of infrastructure development are distributed can reproduce or intensify exclusion of historically marginalised and vulnerable groups¹ [6, 7].

GEDSI understands exclusion as a systemic problem rather than an isolated outcome, manifesting in infrastructure via the processes that shape energy and transport planning, finance, and governance [8, 9]. Currently, GEDSI is infrequently considered in planning processes, and remains fragmented, inconsistent, or tokenistic when reflected in practice [10, 11]. To explore these systemic shortcomings and identify entry points for action, Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) convened a one-day multi-stakeholder workshop at the University of Oxford in March 2025.

The Workshop

Recognising that transformative change requires input from across sectors, the workshop brought together 30 researchers, policymakers, financiers, and practitioners working at the intersection of GEDSI and sustainable development in LMICs. Participants included 10 from research, 6 from policy, 5 from finance, and 9 from development organisations, with representation from the United Kingdom, United States, Denmark, and Kenya.

The workshop was structured around three breakout sessions. In **Breakout Session 1**,

sectoral groups identified factors that prevent the development of equitable energy and transport infrastructure, which were synthesised into 18 consolidated barriers. In **Breakout Session 2**, participants, now in mixed groups, used a simple voting exercise to prioritise these barriers and began discussing how the most critical ones might be addressed in practice. **Breakout Session 3** focused on intersectoral collaboration, with new mixed groups exploring how sectors can work together for effective GEDSI implementation in energy and transport planning.

Results and Discussion

The workshop identified 18 distinct barriers to meaningful GEDSI integration in energy and transport infrastructure, which were grouped into five overarching themes during synthesis: policy and governance, financial and economic, research and expertise, institutional and organisational, and social and cultural. While listed separately for clarity, these barriers are interdependent and mutually reinforcing. The discussion that

follows situates each theme briefly in existing academic and policy literature before turning to the barriers prioritised by workshop participants;

¹ Marginalised and vulnerable groups include but are not limited to: children and youth; ethnic and racial minorities; Indigenous populations; LGBTQIA+ individuals; migrants and refugees; older adults; people with disabilities; people living in informal settlements; people living in poverty; religious minorities; rural communities; and women and girls [5].

references are included to contextualise and support these insights. The most highlighted factor within each theme is bolded and colour coded in red in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Barriers to meaningful GEDSI integration in energy and transport development. Each factor is categorised into five broad themes and listed in descending rank order of significance within each theme. The top factors are bolded and colour coded.

Theme	Factor
Policy and governance	Lack of accountability
	Limited political will
	Misalignment of policy and implementation timelines
	Wider systemic barriers
Financial and economic	Weak business case
	Low funding prioritisation
	Absent or misaligned impact measurement
Research and expertise	Lack of GEDSI data
	Inappropriate communication
	Incapacity
	Technical tool limitations
Institutional and organisational	Lack of just decision-making processes
	Superficial engagement
	Siloed work sectors
	Misunderstanding of GEDSI
Social and cultural	Cultural norms and traditions
	Insufficient outreach and engagement
	Social justice fatigue

Policy and governance: Weak enabling environments

Effective GEDSI implementation in infrastructure development depends on a strong enabling environment, including reliable governance structures, cross-sector coordination, and clear policy mandates [12]. Across many settings – both LMICs and high-income countries (HICs) – such foundations remain underdeveloped or inconsistent [13]. Even where GEDSI frameworks exist, they are often disconnected

from implementation realities, particularly where responsibilities are fragmented across ministries and levels of government, mandates are not matched with dedicated budgets, and implementing agencies lack the data, expertise, or capacity to apply GEDSI consistently [14].

Such frameworks and their implementation are also vulnerable to shifting political priorities, contributing to the side-lining or dilution of GEDSI-related commitments [15, 16]. Moreover, prevailing social and cultural norms can shape which inclusion priorities are seen as politically salient in the first place [17]. Participants noted that some dimensions of inclusion (eg women and girls) may be easier to advance than those perceived as more sensitive or contentious (eg LGBTQIA+ rights).

Within this broader policy context, **lack of accountability** was identified as the most critical barrier. Participants described how, in the absence of formal requirements, standardised metrics, and clear enforcement mechanisms, there is little incentive for institutions to meaningfully engage with GEDSI. Existing standards often remain symbolic and contribute to a superficial, box-ticking approach – a pattern widely observed in inclusive infrastructure governance [18, 19]. Participants further emphasised that accountability must be operationalised through measurable indicators and reporting systems that translate high-level GEDSI commitments into consistent practice across legislative cycles.

Financial and economic: Inadequate economic valuation

Financial decision-makers are critical gatekeepers to infrastructure development, determining which projects are prioritised, resourced, and realised [20, 21]. In many institutions resource constraints, risk aversion, and short-term timelines contribute to

GEDSI being framed as a cost rather than an investment [22, 23]. Traditional financing models rarely include instruments that explicitly support or reward deeper GEDSI alignment, such as conditional loans, outcome-based funding, or incentive-linked products [24, 25].

Against this financial backdrop, the key barrier identified was a **weak business case** for GEDSI. Participants emphasised how, when institutions do not inherently value inclusion and external accountability is limited, the burden falls on advocates to justify GEDSI primarily in economic terms. They stressed that social inclusion benefits are often diffuse, long-term, and difficult to quantify, especially where they intersect complex value chains – a challenge that mirrors wider patterns in impact valuation [26, 27].

At the same time, participants pointed to a growing body of evidence linking inclusion to broader economic gains; for example, analysis by the International Monetary Fund suggests that closing labour force gender gaps could uplift GDP in emerging markets and developing economies by around 23% [28]. This suggests that the ultimate obstacle lies in how value is recognised and measured [29]. The group determined that normalising GEDSI in financial decision-making will require both stronger economic storytelling and a restructuring of incentive systems, so that inclusion is no longer exceptional but expected.

Research and expertise: Lack of comprehensive evidence and GEDSI capacity

Effective GEDSI representation requires a nuanced understanding of the social, cultural, economic, and political contexts in which energy and transport systems operate [30]. However, when GEDSI is not prioritised in policy or institutions, it is consequently deprioritised in research agendas and hiring

practices, contributing to gaps in the practical understanding of who is affected, how exclusion operates, and what works in context – alongside persistent shortages of in-house expertise across sectors [31, 32]. This creates a self-reinforcing cycle: inadequate knowledge and capacity constrain efforts to adapt policy, appraisal, and financing approaches for meaningful GEDSI integration, which, in turn, limits incentives and resources for research needed to close those gaps [8].

The **lack of high-quality disaggregated GEDSI data** was identified as the top barrier within the research context. Without robust data, participants noted that institutions struggle to adapt when interventions fall short, and evaluators lack the tools to measure progress or impact. They highlighted how inconsistent definitions, such as those relating to ‘energy access’, can produce widely varying coverage estimates and render marginalised and vulnerable populations effectively invisible in planning processes, an issue which is well-documented in the literature [33–35]. Participants further stressed that even where relevant research exists, it is often inaccessible due to paywalls, technical language, or misalignment with decision-making timelines; this concern is widely recognised across academia and underscores the need for open, interoperable platforms and more practitioner-oriented communication [36, 37].

Institutional and organisational: Superficial engagement

Public, private, and philanthropic organisations are the actors that ultimately plan, procure, and deliver energy and transport infrastructure [38]. Yet where governance does not set clear GEDSI mandates or enforce accountability, organisational responses can default to superficial engagement: visible activities that signal intent, but rarely reshape priorities, agendas, or budgets [14]. Internal efforts often

default to one-off consultations, generic equity statements, or isolated training sessions. For instance, the Green Climate Fund's independent evaluation detailed how their Gender Action Plans were repeated verbatim in consecutive annual reports, without evidence of implementation [39]. Participants suggested this shortfall is due both to resource constraints and the tendency for GEDSI to be institutionally siloed away from the teams that shape core project decisions.

Building on these organisational challenges, the most salient barrier in this theme was **unjust decision-making processes**. By 'unjust' participants referred to planning processes that systematically privilege the priorities of financiers, technical intermediaries, and political elites over those of affected communities – especially marginalised and vulnerable groups. Participants urged that genuine inclusion requires more than surface-level representation; it demands shifts in who sets agendas, allocates resources, and holds power in decision-making. Leadership bodies remain homogenous across many dimensions (eg ability, gender, and age) with decisions about energy and transport development in LMICs frequently made in HICs, reinforcing power asymmetries and undermining local autonomy [40, 41].

However, participants cautioned that increased representation alone is not sufficient. For example, it is well-documented in literature that the presence of more women in leadership positions does not automatically translate into gender-sensitive or intersectional outcomes [42, 43]. As such, participants pointed to the need for more meaningful engagement with community

organisations and civil society actors who represent GEDSI populations [44].

Social and cultural: Limited awareness and receptivity

Finally, societal attitudes and cultural norms can shape whether GEDSI principles are understood, accepted, or resisted [45]. Deeply rooted beliefs and traditions – whether around gender roles, disability, or sexuality – can limit receptivity to inclusion efforts, particularly where GEDSI is perceived as externally imposed or politically contentious [46, 47]. These dynamics influence community engagement, institutional uptake, political will, and funding priorities, making social and cultural barriers among the most pervasive and difficult to shift [48].

The top barrier in this theme was the persistence of antagonistic **cultural norms and traditions** within the communities where infrastructure is planned and implemented. Participants discussed examples such as the exclusion of women from opportunities in renewable energy value chains or restrictions on their mobility in public spaces, which can limit both their access to services and their participation in emerging economic opportunities. The literature confirms that targeted communication strategies and community engagement can help shift attitudes, clarify misconceptions, and surface shared values [49, 50]. However, participants stressed that prejudiced norms are not confined to LMICs: biases embedded in HIC institutions can similarly undermine efforts to reflect GEDSI throughout the infrastructure planning process [51].

Recommendations: Cross-sector opportunities for action

The barriers identified are deeply interconnected and cannot be addressed by any single actor, sector, or instrument. Discussions in the final breakout session (Breakout Session 3) underscored the need for coordinated cross-sector approaches that link governance, financing, research, institutional practice, and community engagement. Focusing on only one dimension risks failure or inadvertently reinforcing GEDSI barriers in others. The transition towards more inclusive infrastructure must be understood, and approached, as a multidimensional systems challenge requiring proactive and intentional commitment. Three broad opportunities for collaborative action emerged from the workshop, which will be the focus of the second workshop planned for March 2026:

1. Building a case study evidence base

Participants emphasised the utility of compendiums of real-world case studies that demonstrate the impact of GEDSI-integrated infrastructure projects, particularly to engage investors and decision-makers. These should document how inclusive energy and transport projects have been designed, financed, and implemented in different contexts, and highlight both successes and challenges, so that lessons are transferable rather than anecdotal. By systematically documenting and communicating this evidence, such compendiums can directly strengthen the weak business case for GEDSI, normalising inclusion within financial decision-making. They can also help to challenge exclusionary cultural norms by showing how GEDSI-responsive approaches work in practice and deliver benefits for communities. For instance, well-documented examples of women's high-quality participation in the operation of renewable energy infrastructure can help illustrate links between inclusive practices and improved service reliability.

2. Improving knowledge-sharing

Participants also discussed the importance of communicating existing research through accessible platforms. They noted that a great deal of evidence on GEDSI and infrastructure already exists but is fragmented across institutional siloes and often difficult to access or interpret. Interoperable platforms – potentially leveraging established networks in emerging markets – could make existing academic evidence more usable for policymakers, financiers, and practitioners. Over time, shared platforms can create common reference points across sectors and organisations, supporting more coherent policy and organisational responses to GEDSI. For example, such platforms could host shared GEDSI indicators, short practitioner-facing synthesis briefs, or decision-support dashboards designed to align with policy and investment timelines.

3. Aligning methodologies and metrics

Finally, with many parallel GEDSI frameworks already in circulation, participants expressed strong interest in aligning methodologies and developing common metrics to reduce duplication and increase collective impact. Greater methodological coherence would make it easier for governments, funders, and implementers to navigate GEDSI requirements, track progress, and understand where efforts are complementary or overlapping. Aligning frameworks and metrics can reinforce accountability by clarifying what good GEDSI performance looks like and how it will be measured, addressing concerns about symbolic or box-ticking approaches. It also enables funders and governments to compare outcomes across programmes and contexts, helping to reorient incentives towards approaches that demonstrably reduce exclusion. For example, this could include greater consistency in how indicators such as access, affordability, safety, participation in decision-making, or distributional impacts are defined and measured across projects and programmes.

Acknowledgments:

We thank the workshop participants for their generous engagement, candour, and collaborative spirit, which made discussion rigorous and shaped the insights synthesised in this brief.

We also thank Gretel Cuevas Verdin (Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge) and James Dixon (Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, University of Strathclyde) for exceptional peer review feedback; Simon Patterson (Loughborough University) for editorial oversight

and meticulous copyediting; and Sarel Greyling (Sarel Greyling Creative) for the design of this document.

This material has been produced under the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme, which is funded by the UK's Foreign Development and Commonwealth Office (FCDO). However, any views expressed herein do not necessarily reflect the UK government's official policies.

Credit Author Statement:

¹**Marissa Bergman*** (*Institute for Sustainable Resources (ISR), University College London and Department of Engineering Science, University of Oxford*): Conceptualisation, Writing-Original Draft, Writing-Review and Editing

²**Stephanie Hirmer** (*Department of Engineering Science, University of Oxford*): Conceptualisation, Writing-Review and Editing, Project Management

³**Julia Tomei** (*ISR, University College London*): Conceptualisation, Writing-Review and Editing, Project Management

⁴**Beatrice Stockport** (*Department of Engineering Science, University of Oxford*): Conceptualisation, Writing-Review and Editing, Project Management

⁵**Gerald Arhin** (*Department of Science, Technology, Engineering and Public Policy (STeAPP), University College London*): Conceptualisation, Writing-Review and Editing

References

- [1] F. Fuso Nerini *et al.*, "Mapping synergies and trade-offs between energy and the Sustainable Development Goals," *Nat Energy*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 10–15, Nov. 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-017-0036-5>.
- [2] C. Cannone *et al.*, "Addressing Challenges in Long-Term Strategic Energy Planning in LMICs: Learning Pathways in an Energy Planning Ecosystem," *Energies*, vol. 16, no. 21, p. 7267, Oct. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16217267>.
- [3] J. Cronin *et al.*, "Embedding justice in the 1.5°C transition: A transdisciplinary research agenda," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, vol. 1, p. 100001, Aug. 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2021.100001>.
- [4] J. Dixon *et al.*, "How can emerging economies meet development and climate goals in the transport-energy system? Modelling co-developed scenarios in Kenya using a socio-technical approach," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 53, p. 101396, May 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101396>.
- [5] B. Wampler and M. Touchton, "Social Inclusion and Social Justice," in *Voice in Local Development*, 1st ed., Oxford University Press Oxford, 2025, pp. 204–221. Accessed: Aug. 11, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://academic.oup.com/book/59703/chapter/507015511>.

- [6] G. A. Agbaitoro and E. O. Ekhatior, "Just Energy Transition in Africa: Towards Social Inclusion and Environmental Rights-Based Imperatives," *Bus. and hum. rights j.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 34–55, Feb. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/bhj.2024.30>.
- [7] T. J. MacGinley, A. P. Heynen, V. Sharma, and P. A. Lant, "Electricity access advances human development...but not always," *Energy for Sustainable Development*, vol. 88, p. 101770, Oct. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2025.101770>.
- [8] M. Bergman et al., "Guidelines for inclusive and equitable energy and transport modeling," *iScience*, vol. 28, no. 9, p. 113218, Sep. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2025.113218>.
- [9] V. Castán Broto, "Gender Equality and Social Inclusion in Community Energy: An Intersectional Perspective," in *Community Energy and Sustainable Energy Transitions*, V. Castán Broto, Ed., Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 71–93. Accessed: Jun. 23, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-57938-7_4.
- [10] O. W. Johnson et al., "Intersectionality and energy transitions: A review of gender, social equity and low-carbon energy," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 70, p. 101774, Dec. 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101774>.
- [11] M. Buchy and S. Shakya, "Understanding the gap between the gender equality and social inclusion policy and implementation in the energy sector: The case of Nepal," *Energy for Sustainable Development*, vol. 76, p. 101297, Oct. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2023.101297>.
- [12] I. Shittu, A. R. Abdul Latiff, and S. 'Aisyah Baharudin, "Promoting gender equality during uncertainty: which policies and institutional qualities matter?," *IJSE*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 679–697, Apr. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-11-2023-0892>.
- [13] A. Sil and S. Chowdhury, "Do they hear us? A practical framework for designing gender inclusive transport policies in south and southeast Asian countries," *Journal of Transport Geography*, vol. 127, p. 104272, Jul. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2025.104272>.
- [14] J. L. Fuchs, L. A. Onyango, S. Hirmer, and J. Tomei, "Energy, equity and inclusion: Exploring gender equality and social inclusion in energy planning in Kenya," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 130, p. 104432, Dec. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104432>.
- [15] A. Sil, S. Chowdhury, and R. Thoreau, "Challenges and barriers for gender-inclusive public transport policies and practice in Delhi, India," *Case Studies on Transport Policy*, vol. 16, p. 101201, Jun. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cstp.2024.101201>.
- [16] C. Cavoli et al., "Leapfrogging towards sustainable mobility: Policy challenges and opportunities for Sub-Saharan African cities," *Transport Policy*, vol. 171, pp. 513–530, Sep. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2025.06.011>.
- [17] L. L. Delina, S. D. Afable, and C. Chan, "Bridging the rural–urban energy transition divide: Place-specific challenges in renewable energy transitions for vulnerable communities in the Philippines," *World Development Perspectives*, vol. 39, p. 100712, Sep. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wdp.2025.100712>.
- [18] B. Duri and R. Luke, "Transport barriers encountered by people with disability in Africa: An overview," *Journal of Transport and Supply Chain Management*, vol. 16, Oct. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.4102/jtscm.v16i0.826>.
- [19] A. E. Dingil, "Fostering inclusive urban transportation in planning and policy-making: An umbrella review using ALARM methodology," *Sustainable Futures*, vol. 9, p. 100420, Jun. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sftr.2024.100420>.
- [20] I. K. Ofori, N. Ojong, and E. Y. Gbolonyo, "Foreign Aid, Infrastructure, and the Inclusive Growth Agenda in Sub-Saharan Africa," *Growth and Change*, vol. 55, no. 4, p. e70004, Dec. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/grow.70004>.
- [21] L. D. J. Annor, T. Kyei-Mensah, J. A. Addae, M. Robaina, and E. Vieira, "Fostering energy transition in Africa: Financial systems, inclusive growth, corruption control and ICT as catalysts," *Sustainable Environment*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 2518791, Dec. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/27658511.2025.2518791>.
- [22] S. Shome, M. K. Hassan, S. Verma, and T. R. Panigrahi, "Impact investment for sustainable development: A bibliometric analysis," *International Review of Economics & Finance*, vol. 84, pp. 770–800, Mar. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2022.12.001>.

- [23] A. Leonard, K. Nguti, M. Flores Lanza, and S. Hirmer, "Shedding light on vulnerability: Intersectional energy planning for development," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 211, p. 115199, Apr. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.115199>.
- [24] F. Rizzi, C. Pellegrini, and M. Battaglia, "The structuring of social finance: Emerging approaches for supporting environmentally and socially impactful projects," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 170, pp. 805–817, Jan. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.09.167>.
- [25] M. Fay, D. Martimort, and S. Straub, "Funding and financing infrastructure: The joint-use of public and private finance," *Journal of Development Economics*, vol. 150, p. 102629, May 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2021.102629>.
- [26] S. Islam and A. Rahman, "Impact Investment Deal Flow and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): 'Mind the Gap?'," *SSRN Journal*, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4362794>.
- [27] L. Hansson and C. Ho, "Workshop 7b report: Sustainable transport systems designed to meet the needs of both users and residents," *Research in Transportation Economics*, vol. 111, p. 101579, Jun. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.retrec.2025.101579>.
- [28] L. Kolovich, M. Newiak, D. Gomes, J. Gu, V. Malta, and J. Mondragon, "Why a Gender Lens Matters: Unlocking Solutions to Macroeconomic Challenges," International Monetary Fund (IMF), Washington, DC, NOTE/2024/003, Oct. 2024. Accessed: Jan. 28, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://www.imf.org/-/media/files/publications/gns/2024/english/gnsea2024003.pdf>.
- [29] T. O. Aluko and B. S. Ngubane, "The Role of Infrastructure Investment on Inclusive Growth and Human Development Index: Evidence from Emerging Economies," *IJEFI*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 219–231, Oct. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijefi.16654>.
- [30] L. Sagaris and I. Tiznado-Aitken, "New horizons for sustainable transport planning: An analysis of seven years of gender-related research in Chile," *Journal of Transport & Health*, vol. 28, p. 101544, Jan. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2022.101544>.
- [31] C. E. B. Cannon and E. K. Chu, "Gender, sexuality, and feminist critiques in energy research: A review and call for transversal thinking," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 75, p. 102005, May 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102005>.
- [32] T. Bagdi, S. Ghosh, A. Sarkar, A. K. Hazra, S. Balachandran, and S. Chaudhury, "Evaluation of research progress and trends on gender and renewable energy: A bibliometric analysis," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 423, p. 138654, Oct. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138654>.
- [33] S. Bradshaw, "Sex disaggregation alone will not energize equality," *Nat Energy*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 813–815, Sep. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-018-0247-4>.
- [34] M. W. Judson, S. Johnstone, and M. McPherson, "Development of data-driven insights using energy system models: A systematic scoping review," *Energy Strategy Reviews*, vol. 62, p. 101880, Nov. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2025.101880>.
- [35] S. Hirmer *et al.*, "Inconsistent measurement calls into question progress on electrification in sub-Saharan Africa," *Nat Energy*, Sep. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-024-01609-4>.
- [36] A. Beltramo, A. Leonard, J. Tomei, and W. Usher, "Data governance and open science in energy planning: A case study of the Kenyan ecosystem," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 118, p. 103821, Dec. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103821>.
- [37] M. Eklund, K. Khalilpour, A. Voinov, and M. J. Hossain, "Community microgrids: A decision framework integrating social capital with business models for improved resiliency," *Applied Energy*, vol. 367, p. 123458, Aug. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123458>.
- [38] J. Radtke, "Understanding the Complexity of Governing Energy Transitions: Introducing an Integrated Approach of Policy and Transition Perspectives," *Env Pol Gov*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 595–614, Aug. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.2158>.
- [39] Independent Evaluation Unit, "Independent Synthesis of the GCF's Gender Approach," Green Climate Fund, Songdo, South Korea, Sep. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ieu.greenclimate.fund/sites/default/files/document/ieu-gender-synthesis-2.pdf>.
- [40] M. Ali, L. C. Couto, S. Unsworth, and R. Debnath, "Bridging the divide in energy policy research: Empirical evidence from global collaborative networks," *Energy Policy*, vol. 173, p. 113380, Feb. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.215810.1016/j.enpol.2022.113380>.

- [41] J. L. Fuchs, M. Tesfamichael, R. Clube, and J. Tomei, "How does energy modelling influence policymaking? Insights from low- and middle-income countries," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 203, p. 114726, Oct. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.215810.1016/j.rser.2024.114726>.
- [42] M. Mansour, M. Al Zobi, D. A. E'leimat, S. Abu Alim, and M. I. Tabash, "Female leadership, gender boards and environmental innovation: Comprehensive evidence from the global energy sector," *Innovation and Green Development*, vol. 4, no. 4, p. 100275, Aug. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.215810.1016/j.igd.2025.100275>.
- [43] J. Lieu, A. H. Sorman, O. W. Johnson, L. D. Virla, and B. P. Resurrección, "Three sides to every story: Gender perspectives in energy transition pathways in Canada, Kenya and Spain," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 68, p. 101550, Oct. 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101550>.
- [44] M. J. W. A. Vanderschuren and O. A. Nnene, "Inclusive planning: African policy inventory and South African mobility case study on the exclusion of persons with disabilities," *Health Res Policy Sys*, vol. 19, no. 1, p. 124, Dec. 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-021-00775-1>.
- [45] O. Muza and V. M. Thomas, "Cultural norms to support gender equity in energy development: Grounding the productive use agenda in Rwanda," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 89, p. 102543, Jul. 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102543>.
- [46] M. Dzidzai, T. Nyanga, and M. N. Naong, "Exploring the challenges and solutions for cultivating an inclusive work environment in the energy sector in Zimbabwe," *IJRBS*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 115–123, Jul. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v14i4.3991>.
- [47] S. Fankhauser et al., "A 10-point plan to scale up renewable energy in the Global South," *Climate Policy*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 938–946, Jul. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2024.2418948>.
- [48] C. Alda-Vidal, R. Khalid, C. Foulds, S. Royston, and M. Greene, "Gender imaginaries in energy transitions: How professionals construct and envision gender equity in energy access in the Global South," *World Development*, vol. 168, p. 106258, Aug. 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2023.106258>.
- [49] R. R. Das, R. Sussman, and R. Carlson, "Trust in scientists, researchers, and environmental organizations associated with policy support for energy transition," *Energy and Climate Change*, vol. 6, p. 100179, Dec. 2025, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egycc.2025.100179>.
- [50] O. Osunmuyiwa and H. Ahlborg, "Inclusiveness by design? Reviewing sustainable electricity access and entrepreneurship from a gender perspective," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 53, pp. 145–158, Jul. 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.03.010>.
- [51] E. Üstündağlı Erten, E. B. Güzeloğlu, P. Ifaei, K. Khalilpour, P. Ifaei, and C. Yoo, "Decoding intersectionality: A systematic review of gender and energy dynamics under the structural and situational effects of contexts," *Energy Research & Social Science*, vol. 110, p. 103432, Apr. 2024, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103432>.